

Spectrophotometric Study of Chelate Formation of Tetravalent Hafnium with Chromotrope 2R

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Spectrophotometric investigations indicate the formation of 1 : 1 chelate between Hf(IV) and chromotrope 2R in aqueous solution. The chelate is stable between pH range 1.0 to 3.0. The average values of log K and free energy of formation at constant ionic strength ($I = 0.1$) were found to be of the order of 4.4 ± 0.1 and -6.0 ± 0.1 respectively at 25°, the $\lambda_{\max}$ of the violet chelate being 530 nm.

The disodium salt of phenylazo chromotropic acid (Chromotrope 2R, abbreviated as CTR) is an excellent chromogenic agent in the photometric determination of various metals including some rare earths¹⁻⁹. Recently we have found it to be a sensitive reagent for Zr(IV)¹⁰. In the present communication the composition, nature and stability constant of Hf(IV) : CTR chelate is reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions of hafnium chloride (Johnson, Matthey and Co.) chromotrope 2R, BDH and sodium perchlorate (Riedel) were prepared by dissolving the respective compounds in double distilled water.

Hitachi Perkin Elmer Uv-Vis spectrophotometer (Model 139) was used for absorbance measurements and for pH measurements a Beckman H2 pH meter was employed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It has been observed that order of addition of reactants had no appreciable effect on absorbance. The colour system adhere to Beer's law over a concentration range of 0.14 to 1.17 p.p.m of Hf. The sensitivity of the colour reaction as defined by Sandell and molar extinction co-efficient were 0.0215 ug/cm² and 7125 respectively at 580 nm.

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To find the nature of the chelate formed, Vosburgh and Cooper¹¹ method was adopted. For this, mixtures containing different proportions of hafnyl chloride and CTR were prepared at $pH\ 2.0 \pm 0.1$ and the absorbances measured. The absorbance values of different mixtures are plotted against wavelength in Fig. 1. It is found that only one chelate is formed under conditions of study.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of mixtures of Hafnyl Chloride and Chromotrope 2R at $pH\ 2.0 \pm 0.1$.

A, $c' = 4.0 \times 10^{-5}M$	
B, $c = 4.0 \times 10^{-5}M$	$p = 1$
C, $c = 1.6 \times 10^{-4}M$	$p = 0.25$
D, $c = 4.0 \times 10^{-5}M$	$p = 3.0$

The chelate is formed between $pH\ 1.0$ to 3.0 and it gives a constant optical density in pH range 1.8 to 2.4 . Hence a $pH\ 2.0 \pm 0.1$ was selected for subsequent studies.

Composition of the chelate: The composition of the chelate was established by the method of continuous variations¹² and mole ratio method¹³. A large number of observations were taken at $580\ nm$ (because at this wavelength difference in absorbance is maximum and the absorbance of the reagent is minimum) and some of the results are shown in Figs. 2, 3 and 4.

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FIG 2

Fig. 2. Absorption of equimolar solutions of Hafnium Chloride and Chromotrope 2R at 580 nm ($p = 1$, $pH = 2.0 \pm 0.1$)

- A, $c = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$
- B, $c = 1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$
- C, $c = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$

FIG 3

Fig. 3. Absorption of non-equimolar solutions of Hafnium Chloride and Chromotrope 2R at 580 nm, $pH = 2.0 \pm 0.1$.

- A, $c = 2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ $p = 0.5$
- B, $c = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ $p = 2.0$

FIG 4

Fig. 4. Mole ratio method at $pH = 2.0 \pm 0.1$

- CTR, $c' = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$
- curve A = 570 nm
- curve B = 580 nm.

Table I summarises the results on the composition as arrived from the examination of Figs. 2 and 3. In these Figs. c represents the concentration of hafnium and p, the ratio a'/c , c' being the concentration of CTR.

TABLE I

Composition of the chelate from continuous variation method

Total volume = 25 ml.

Fig.	Curve	$C \times 10^{-4}$	p	wavelength nm	Volume Hf (IV) at peak (ml)	Composition of the chelate Hf(IV) : CTR
2	A	2.00	1.0	580	12.5	1 : 1
	B	1.25	1.0	580	12.5	1 : 1
	C	1.00	1.0	580	12.5	1 : 1
3	A	2.00	2.00	580	7.5	1 : 1
	B	2.50	0.50	580	16.0	1 : 1

It is clear from the above table that the ratio of Hf : CTR in the chelate is 1 : 1.

Results obtained by the other method viz., the mole ratio method (Fig. 4) corroborate the same composition.

Evaluation of stability constant : The apparent stability constant was calculated from the absorbance data by the method of (a) Banerji and Dey¹⁴, (b) continuous variation method using nonequimolecular solutions, (c) mole ratio method, and (d) molecular extinction coefficient.

TABLE II

Stability constant of Hf(IV) : CTR chelate

Temp. = 25° Ionic strength (I) = 0.1 pH = 2.0 ± 0.1

Method	log K	ΔG° k cal/mole
(a)	4.5 ± 0.1	-6.1 ± 0.1
(b)	4.3 ± 0.1	-5.9 ± 0.1
(c)	4.5 ± 0.2	-6.1 ± 0.2
(d)	4.4 ± 0.1	-6.0 ± 0.1

Suggestion on the structure of the chelate : The chelate is anionic in nature as has been noted by the complete adsorption by the ion exchange resin Amberlite I.R.-45 OH.

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